

Second order derivative linear-sweep polarographic determination of capecitabine in pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : A sensitive electrochemical method for the determination of anticancer drug capecitabine (CPT) was established, by using the second order derivative linear-sweep polarography. A well-defined reduction peak of CPT was observed at the potential of -1.19 V in pH 5.0 Britton-Robinson (BR) buffer, which was attributed to the reduction of carbonyl group with the N-C bond cleavage on the mercury electrode. The optimal conditions for the CPT determination were optimized. Under the selected conditions the reduction peak currents were found to be linearly dependent on the CPT concentration in the range from 1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-5} mol/L with the detection limit 8.53×10^{-8} mol/L (3σ). This proposed method was further applied to determine the CPT contents in Xeloda tablet sample successfully.

Keywords : Capecitabine, second order derivative, linear-sweep, polarography, electrochemistry.

Introduction

Capacetabine (CPT), which is chemically named as *N*₄-pentoxycarbonyl-5'-deoxy-5-fluorocytidine with the molecular structure shown in Scheme 1, is an oral tumor-selective fluoropyrimidine carbamate approved in the treatment of colorectal and breast cancer¹⁻³. This drug displays a pharmacokinetic characterization of high gastrointestinal absorption and then converts to its metabolites by a complete enzymatic catalysis^{4,5}. CPT shows relatively specific organ expression because it can be sequentially metabolized to 5-fluorouracil by carboxylesterase, cytidine deaminase and thymidine phosphorylase with improved selectivity toward tumors and less adverse effects^{6,7}. So it is necessary to establish a sensitive method for the CPT determination. The assay of CPT in biological fluids and pharmaceutical formulations has been developed with different analytical methods such as high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)⁸⁻¹⁰, liquid chromatography-ultraviolet detection (LC-UV)¹¹, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)^{12,13}, high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS)¹⁴ and spectrophotometry¹⁵, some of which require long analysis time, elaborate extraction and

purification steps or on-line sample extraction with expensive instruments.

Scheme 1. The molecular structure of CPT.

Compared with the above methods, electrochemical techniques have been widely used in the drug analysis with the advantages such as high sensitivity and selectivity, low cost of the apparatus, facile and fast operation, relatively short operation time¹⁶. For example Saddiqui *et al.* applied direct current polarography and differential pulse polarography for the detections of vitamins in pharmaceutical formulations¹⁷. The electrochemical behaviors of drug on different kinds of working electrode can

also provide the related redox mechanism in its metabolic process and establish alternative analytical method for the drug samples. Polarography is a traditional electrochemical method for the trace analysis with inherent advantages concerning speed, simplicity and sensitivity. Also with the usage of dropping mercury electrode (DME) as the working electrode, the electrochemical response is very reproducible without the interference of the fouling process or the past history¹⁸.

In this paper a new electroanalytical method was proposed for the CPT determination with simple polarographic method. The second order derivative linear sweep polarography is used throughout in all the experiments, which is more sensitive and selective than the traditional linear sweep polarography and a very sharp peak shape polarographic curve can be achieved. Under the selected conditions CPT exhibited a sensitive reduction peak on the mercury electrode. Based on the reduction of CPT, the electroanalytical procedure for the determination of CPT in formulation samples was further described.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A model JP-303 polarographic analyzer (Chengdu Instrumental Factory, China) was used for polarographic detection with a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as the working electrode, an Ag/AgCl electrode as the reference electrode and a platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode. The instrumental conditions for the detection were selected as follows : initial potential : -0.80 V; mercury drop standing time : 15 s and potential scanning rate : 800 mV/s. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature (24 ± 1 °C).

Reagents :

A 1.0×10^{-2} mol/L stock solution of capecitabine (CPT, Jiangsu Farmtec Research Co. Ltd., China) was prepared in water and stored in a 4 °C refrigerator. Working solutions of CPT were prepared daily by diluting the stock solution with supporting electrolyte. 0.2 mol/L Britton-Robinson (BR) buffer was used as the supporting electrolyte, which was prepared by diluting 12.35 g H_3BO_4 , 13.55 mL H_3PO_4 and 11.80 mL CH_3COOH to 1000 mL with distilled water and adjusted to appropriate pH using 0.5 mol/L NaOH. All the other chemicals used

in the experiment were of analytical grade and doubly distilled water was used for the preparation of solution.

The procedure for preparing tablet samples :

Xeloda tablet sample (500 mg per tablet), were purchased from Shanghai Roche Pharmaceutical Co. Ltd. (YBH08582008). One tablet was weighed accurately and ground to a fine powder, transferred to a 25 mL flask and diluted to the scale with distilled water. After sonicating 15 min for the complete dissolution, the sample solution was got and further diluted with pH 5.0 BR buffer solution in a 10 mL calibration tube.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical behavior of CPT :

In order to improve the sensitivity of the determination, the second order derivative linear sweep polarography is used because it can exhibit sharp peak shape compared with the traditional normal linear sweep polarography. The experimental results of the relationship between the d^2i/dE^2 with E can also be automatically recorded by the JP 303 polarographic analyzer. So the peak current measured is demonstrated as I_p'' , which means the d^2i/dE^2 value. The typical second order derivative linear sweep polarograms of CPT were recorded with the results shown in Fig. 1. Curve a is the polarogram of BR buffer solution without any polarographic peak. Curve b is the polarogram of 5.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT solution, which gave a well-defined polarographic reductive peak at the potential of -1.19 V (vs Ag/AgCl). With further increase of

Fig. 1. Second-order linear sweep polarograms of BR buffer (a), 5.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT (b) and 1.0×10^{-5} mol/L CPT (c) in pH 5.0 BR buffer with the scan rate of 800 mV/s.

the CPT concentration to 1.0×10^{-5} mol/L, the reduction peak current also increased correspondingly without any change of the reduction peak potential (Curve c). So the reduction peak was attributed to the electrochemical reduction of CPT on the mercury electrode.

Effect of pH :

The effect of buffer pH on the electrochemical response of 5.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT was investigated in the pH range from 2.0 to 9.0. The relationships of reduction peak current and potential with pH were further explored with the results shown in Fig. 2. The solution pH obviously influenced the reduction peak current and the current increased with the solution pH in the range from 3.0 to 5.0, and then decreased with the buffer pH more than 5.0 (Fig. 2A). Since the maximum current response was obtained at pH 5.0, this pH was chosen for the subsequent experiments. The reduction peak potential (E_p) of CPT was negatively shifted with the increase of buffer pH (Fig. 2B), indicating that protons took part in the electrochemical reduction reaction. The relationship between E_p and pH was established with the linear regression equation expressed as E_p (V) = -0.055 pH - 0.912 ($n = 8$, $\gamma = 0.994$). A slope value of -55 mV/pH was close to the theoretical value of -59 mV/pH, indicated that there were the equal numbers of protons and electrons involved in electrode reaction.

The effect of BR buffer amounts on the electrochemical response of 5.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT was also investigated. The reduction peak current increased with the addition of BR buffer gradually. So 0.2 mol/L BR buffer solution was selected as the supporting electrolyte in the experiment.

Effect of scan rate :

The influence of scan rate on the electrochemical response of 5.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT was also investigated. The reduction peak current increased gradually with the scan rate in the range from 200 to 800 mV/s and a linear regression equation was got as $I_p''(\mu\text{A}) = 3.017 v$ (V/s) - 0.208 ($n = 10$, $\gamma = 0.999$). The results indicated that the reduction of CPT at DME was an adsorption-controlled process. Also the reduction peak potential (E_p) shifted negatively with the increase of scan rate. The reduction peak potential and $\log v$ exhibited a good linear relationship with the regression equation as E_p (V) = -0.0536

Fig. 2. Influence of pH on the reduction peak current (A) and potential (B) of 5.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT with the scan rate of 800 mV/s.

$\log v - 1.188$ ($n = 10$, $\gamma = 0.998$). According to the equation¹⁹,

$$E_p = E^0 + \frac{2.303RT}{\alpha nF} \left[\log \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} k^0 - \log v \right]$$

where n is the number of electrons, α is the charge transfer coefficient, v is the scan rate, E^0 is the formal potential, other symbols have their usual meanings. Based on the relationship of E_p and $\log v$, the value of αn was calculated as 1.10. Generally α can be assumed as 0.5 for a totally irreversible electrode process, so the number of electron transferred (n) in the electro-reduction of CPT was got as 2.20, which was in accordance with the reported value¹⁵. Since the number of electrons and protons involved in the electrode process of CPT is equal, then the electro-reduction of CPT on the mercury electrode is a two-electron and two-proton process. The 5'-deoxy-5-fluorouridine part in the CPT molecule could not be reduced under the selected conditions¹⁵. While the

carbonyl group is likely to be protonated due to the high polarity in the pH 5.0 BR solution, then the reduction will take place by N–C bond cleavage to give the free amino group. So the possible electro-reduction mechanism of CPT was proposed in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Proposed electro-reduction mechanism of CPT.

Effect of instrumental conditions :

The scan rate and the standing time of the mercury drop of the instrument were studied. The peak current increased with the increase of the potential scan rate from 200 to 800 mV/s and the mercury drop standing time from 5 to 15 s. When the dropping mercury time was more than 15 s, the mercury drop would fall down automatically from the electrode. So scan rate and the standing time of the instrument were selected as 800 mV/s and 15 s, respectively.

Working curve :

Under the optimal determination conditions, the calibration curve for the determination of CPT was constructed based on the reduction peak current versus the concentration of CPT. Good linearity can be found in the range from 1.0×10^{-7} mol/L to 1.0×10^{-5} mol/L with the linear regression equation as $I_p''(\mu\text{A}) = 0.131C (\mu\text{mol/L}) + 0.116$ ($n = 9$, $\gamma = 0.993$), where $I_p''(\mu\text{A})$ is the second order derivative linear sweep reduction peak current and C is the concentration of CPT. The detection limit of this assay was given by $3S_0/S$, where 3 is the factor at the 99% confidential level, S_0 the standard deviation of the blank measurements without CPT ($n = 9$) and S the slope of the calibration curve. The detection limit was calculated as 8.53×10^{-8} mol/L, which is lower than a reported value of 1.13×10^{-7} mol/L²⁰.

Interference studies :

To evaluate the selectivity of this method, the influence of some possible interfering substances such as amino acid, nucleotide and common inorganic ions on the determination of 1.0×10^{-6} mol/L CPT was performed in the pH 5.0 BR buffer solution and the results were shown in Table 1, which indicated that the presence of 50-fold concentration of these substances had less influence on the CPT determination. The results indicated the method exhibited good selection for CPT determination.

Table 1. Influences of interfering substances on the determination of 1.0 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ CPT

Interfering substances	Concentration (mol/L)	RSD (%)
L-Cysteine	5.0×10^{-5}	-3.56
L-Arginine	5.0×10^{-5}	-2.93
L-Tyrosine	5.0×10^{-5}	-1.81
L-Tryptophan	5.0×10^{-5}	-2.52
Glycine	5.0×10^{-5}	-4.31
L-Valine	5.0×10^{-5}	-3.53
Cytosine	5.0×10^{-5}	-3.85
Uracil	5.0×10^{-5}	-4.28
Thymine	5.0×10^{-5}	-2.93
Mg ²⁺	5.0×10^{-5}	-3.75
Zn ²⁺	5.0×10^{-5}	-4.14

Determination of CPT in pharmaceutical tablets :

The proposed method was applied to the assay of CPT content in Xeloda tablet sample (500 mg per tablet). The content of the CPT in tablet was determined based on the calibration curve with the detection results shown in Table 1. The recovery test was performed by the standard addition method to evaluate the accuracy of the method. It can be seen that the results were satisfactory with the recovery in the range from 97.4 to 103.8%, showing that the proposed method could be efficiently applied to CPT determination in commercial pharmaceutical samples.

Table 2. Determination of CPT in Xeloda tablet sample ($n = 9$)

Labeled (mg)	Detected (mg)	Added (mg)	Found (mg)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
	498.6	50.0	547.3	97.4	3.32
500.0	501.2	40.0	542.7	103.8	4.05
	503.6	30.0	533.6	100.2	3.92

Conclusions :

The electrochemical determination of anticancer drug CPT was established and applied to the Xeloda tablet sample detection. CPT exhibited an irreversible and pH dependent electrochemical process on the mercury electrode. Electrochemical parameters of CPT were calculated with the electro-reduction mechanism proposed. Meanwhile the optimal conditions for CPT determination were selected. Under the optimized conditions CPT can be sensitive detected in the concentration range from 1.0×10^{-7} mol/L to 1.0×10^{-5} mol/L with the detection limit as 8.53×10^{-8} mol/L (3σ). The proposed method is rapid, requiring less time to run a sample with good precision and accuracy. The detection of Xeloda tablet samples was satisfactory with good recovery, indicating the practical application of this method.

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